

Distributed Control and Communications for Grid Systems

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Abstract—A major problem of the grid system is identifying the source of abnormal behaviors. It is particularly important to identify the areas in which the grid system suffers from power deficiencies due to fault or voltage instability. Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) are capable of measuring current and voltage amplitudes and phase angles, which can then be effectively used to monitor the power quality. This would require the support of a communication network to detect regions in the grid that may suffer from voltage instability. In this paper we present a distributed mapping technique that is based on a hierarchical network structure to identify the proximity of the grid instability for any possible remedial control action at the local level. For voltage monitoring, we also develop an average standard deviation measurement technique to access the power quality. We use the IEEE 34 bus grid distribution model and the IEEE 39 bus transmission model to assess the performance of the proposed techniques.

Keywords—Smart Grid, synchrophasors, PMU, hierarchical networks, distribution grid, fault location, dendrogram

I. INTRODUCTION

A major challenge for future wide area measurement systems is how to respond securely and reliably to various disturbances in the next generation of power grid networks. With an ever increasing deployment of Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) in the power system, the dynamic has shifted towards situational awareness through a wide area measurement system. A key aspect of situational awareness is to gather knowledge of the power grid status by providing synchronous measurement data at sensitive locations. While PMUs are highly capable of providing synchronous measurement data, a major obstacle is processing and controlling the vast amount of data arriving at the power grid control center. Currently, nearly 1,000 PMUs are being deployed in North America and this trend is continuing with a fast pace. While the main objective of PMU deployment is to improve monitoring and dynamic control of the power grid, a new opportunity is emerging by applying such measurements in the distributed grid system. Unlike high voltage transmission their expansion for deployment in medium-to-low voltage distribution systems is facing many challenges [1]. One major obstacle is that the distribution grid suffers from noise and harmonics and this could severely impact the accuracy of the phasor measurements. In addition, in the presence of non-linear loads and renewable resources the distribution grid can suffer from excessive reactive power that causes voltage instability. This would require injecting reactive power of an opposite type

at the local level since reactive power cannot be transported over long distances due to significant transmission loss. Hence, voltage regulators are normally distributed along the feeder so that they can adjust the voltage to a desirable level (e.g., + or -5% of the nominal voltage). For example, a capacitors bank can be used to compensate reactive power caused by the inductive load for controlling the voltage level. This would be at the expense of magnifying harmonics, which could make it difficult to estimate the line frequency, as well as measure the phase angle between voltage and current in order to measure the power factor (PF).

It should be noted that voltage instability may also be caused by faults, such as tripping of lines, short circuits, etc. While there are methods that can be applied to distinguish between faults and voltage fluctuations caused by reactive power [1, 2, 3], the initial task would be to locate the proximity of the problem regardless of its nature. In other words, voltage instability is a local phenomenon and any remedial action would require the support of a communication network with an integrated control strategy. For example, a communication network infrastructure should be capable of providing access to the sensitive locations where PMUs are placed. The wireless hierarchical network infrastructure proposed in [4] is one such example where a Phasor Data Concentrator (PDC) at each local level collects phasor data information from its associated PMU. In this structure, the aggregated data at the local PDC is then forwarded to the next hierarchical PDC level. The number of hierarchical levels depends on the control strategy and the placement of the synchrophasor devices throughout the grid network. More importantly, the hierarchical structure would allow a PDC at each level not only to act as a local controller, but also reduce the data information that would be needed for transportation to the next level [4]. While such a network has the ability to provide wireless communication access at the local level, the challenge of how to detect and identify voltage problems at the lowest possible PDC level remains.

The main thrust of this paper is develop methods to evaluate the link quality at the PDC level, where any protective control action can take place locally, rather than at the control center. Therefore, in this paper we propose a mapping technique that can allow the local PDC to identifying the regions in the grid that are affected by voltage fluctuations. We also present techniques that can be applied to classify the synchrophasor data into distinct categories: normal or abnormal and subsequently detect links that may suffer from voltage fluctuations. After applying the proposed neighborhood map the effect of voltage instability can then be evaluated using a standard deviation of voltage fluctuations algorithm to monitor the power quality. We use our

real-time wireless-based hierarchical network testbed to assess the proposed techniques. In this testbed, which is based on the emulation platform, typical IEEE power grid models are used to locate the main source of instability in the network. In the following section, after a brief review of the wireless hierarchical synchrophasor network, we present our proposed mapping technique. Section III describes the algorithm proposed to detect regions that are affected by grid disturbances. In Section IV the IEEE 34 Bus model for distribution and the IEEE 34 bus model for transmission are used to evaluate the proposed schemes.

II. PROPOSED MAPPING SCHEME

Our main objective is to take advantage of the hierarchical synchrophasor structure to monitor the network at lower PDC levels with the capability of identifying buses/lines that suffer from power disturbances such as faults or voltage instability. Numerous researches has been carried out in the field of fault detection and control [5, 6, 7]. However, most of the works are performed in centralized manner. For example, in a large power grid system, all computations and monitoring for any fault detection have to be carried out at the central PDC (e.g., Super PDC). In this paper, the proposed hierarchical disturbance detection aims at identifying and initiating any preventive control action locally and in a timely manner.

For both transmission and distribution grids we assume PMUs are placed at sensitive locations so that the voltage, current, and reactive power can be directly observed. Bear in mind that distribution networks suffer severely from the dynamic activities caused by fluctuation of the voltage level in the presence of renewable generation and nonlinear loads. Moreover, unlike transmission networks which are mainly based in mesh structure, distribution networks use radial or loop where renewable generators are widely dispersed along the feeders. It is also important to note that distribution characteristics, such as feeder impedance, power flows, and harmonic distortion, are vastly different from those of transmission networks. Nonetheless, in order to detect faulty connections or areas with poor power quality (e.g., droop characteristics), a local map is formed at each PDC level. As any power disturbance, such as voltage fluctuation, can also effect the power profile of neighboring regions, the objective is to identify a faulty region between a pair of neighboring PMU nodes. The local map is constructed by assigning a so-called a neighboring ID to PMU nodes reporting to their local PDC. As an example, Fig. 1 shows a network consisting of two local PDCs: PDC A and PDC B where both report to the next level PDC, i.e., Regional PDC (RPDC). According to this figure, the PDC-A and PDC-B have 6 and 5 PMUs, respectively. The local map of PDC-A is furnished with the neighbor IDs of its associated PMUs. Furthermore, if the neighbor PMU reports to another PDC, its ID is followed by its respective PDC ID as shown in Table 1.

As can be seen from Fig. 1, any disturbance caused by a fault or voltage instability may also impact the neighboring areas represented by their respective PMUs. If a disturbance is detected by a PMU where all its neighboring PMUs report to the same local PDC, this PDC through its local map would be able to identify the faulty bus locally. For example, if PMU A2 and PMU A4 have been identified as having abnormal behavior, the

Fig. 1: Hierarchical synchrophasor network with two local PDCs

Table 1: Local maps for hierarchical disturbance detection

For local PDC-A:

	Neighboring PMUs
PMU A1	PMU A2-ID, PMU A3-ID
PMU A2	PMU A1-ID, PMU A4-ID
PMU A3	PMU A1-ID, PMU A4-ID
PMU A4	PMU A2-ID, PMU A3-ID, PMU A6-ID
PMU A5	PMU A2-ID, PMU A6-ID
PMU A6	PMU A4-ID, PMU A5-ID, PMU B1-ID-PDC B_ID

For local PDC-B:

	Neighboring PMUs
PMU B1	PMU B2-ID, PMU B3-ID, PMU A6-ID-PDC A_ID
PMU B2	PMU B1-ID, PMU B4-ID
PMU B3	PMU B1-ID, PMU B2-ID, PMU B5-ID
PMU B4	PMU B2-ID, PMU B5-ID
PMU B5	PMU B2-ID, PMU B4-ID

region between the two PMUs can be identified by the PDC-A.

On the other hand, if two abnormal neighboring PMUs are associated to different local PDCs, their respective PDC, based on their local maps, will forward the PMU data for link assessment to the next PDC level (e.g., RPDC in Fig. 1). For example, if a disturbance occurs in a link connecting PMU A6 and PMU B1, the local PDC-A will detect the abnormal A6 and its connection to PMU B1, as indicated in its local map. Local PDC-A will then report PMU A6's information to RPDC for further evaluation. Similarly, PDC-B, by checking its own local map, will forward the PMU B1 data to the RPDC. Under these conditions, RPDC would be able to declare the area between PMU A6 and PMU B1 as a faulty region. If necessary, the identified region may undergo further assessment to pinpoint the exact location of the fault [8].

Another important consideration is to how to classify PMU data as normal or abnormal. There are a number of criteria, namely: frequency, voltage amplitude, current amplitude and power factor (PF) that can be used to assess the power quality at each PMU node. While each criterion needs to be carefully examined, in our investigation we use voltage amplitudes to

detect abnormal PMU. For example, based on Figure 1, let $V_i^{PDC-A} = [V_{t-n}^{A1} \dots V_t^{A1} \dots V_{t+n}^{A1}]$ represent an observation vector of the PDC-A i th node (e.g., $i=1, 2, \dots$) that corresponds to voltage measurements at $N=2n+1$ consecutive time slots. Note that such data, depending on the PDC buffer size, can be retrieved at each PDC [4].

For a grid system, a local observation matrix for each local PDC can then be formed. For PDC A with a K number of PMUs, this can be shown as:

$$V^{PDC-A} = \begin{bmatrix} V_{t-n}^{A1} & \dots & V_t^{A1} & \dots & V_{t+n}^{A1} \\ V_{t-n}^{A2} & \dots & V_t^{A2} & \dots & V_{t+n}^{A2} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ V_{t-n}^{AK} & \dots & V_t^{AK} & \dots & V_{t+n}^{AK} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

Similar matrices can also be obtained for other PDCs in the grid system. For each observation matrix we then obtain a row vector, M , containing the mean value of each column. For PDC-A, for instance, we can show:

$$M^A = \left[\frac{(V_{t-n}^{A1} + V_{t-n}^{A2} \dots + V_{t-n}^{AK})}{K} \dots \frac{(V_t^{A1} + V_t^{A2} \dots + V_t^{AK})}{K} \dots \frac{(V_{t+n}^{A1} + V_{t+n}^{A2} \dots + V_{t+n}^{AK})}{K} \right]$$

Or

$$M^A = [m_{t-n} \dots m_t \dots m_{t+n}]. \quad (2)$$

For each PDC we then calculate the local standard deviation for every node. For PDC A this is shown below

$$SDF_{A1} = \sqrt{(V_{t-n}^{A1} - m_{t-n})^2 + \dots + (V_t^{A1} - m_t)^2 + \dots + (V_{t+n}^{A1} - m_{t+n})^2}$$

$$SDF_{A2} = \sqrt{(V_{t-n}^{A2} - m_{t-n})^2 + \dots + (V_t^{A2} - m_t)^2 + \dots + (V_{t+n}^{A2} - m_{t+n})^2}$$

$$\dots$$

$$SDF_{AK} = \sqrt{(V_{t-n}^{AK} - m_{t-n})^2 + \dots + (V_t^{AK} - m_t)^2 + \dots + (V_{t+n}^{AK} - m_{t+n})^2} \quad (3)$$

Where SDF_{A1} , SDF_{A2} , \dots and SDF_{AK} represent PMU nodes' Standard Deviation Factor (SDF).

Next, we define Group Instability Factor (GIF) for each local PDC and this is based on averaging their SDFs. For example, for PDC-A, PDC-B, and PDC-C each with K , L and Q PMUs, their GIFs can be shown as,

$$GIF^A = (SDF_{A1} + SDF_{A2} + SDF_{A3} \dots SDF_{AK}) / K$$

$$GIF^B = (SDF_{B1} + SDF_{B2} + SDF_{B3} \dots SDF_{BL}) / L \quad (4)$$

$$GIF^C = (SDF_{C1} + SDF_{C2} + SDF_{C3} \dots SDF_{CQ}) / Q$$

III. VOLTAGE INSTABILITY ASSESSMENT PROCEDURE

The Group Instability Factors (GIF) defined in (4) are then used to monitor and detect links/regions that may suffer from voltage instability or a fault. The first step is to find PDCs with high GIFs. If a GIF value is larger than a predefined threshold, the area covered by this PDC will be marked as the "unstable local area". It is possible that a fault may occur in a region between two neighboring nodes, each reporting to a different PDC (e.g., A6 and B1 in Fig. 1). Under such a condition both regions' GIFs are expected to exceed the pre-defined threshold. For a local PDC with a GIF exceeding a pre-defined threshold, the first step is to identify a link/region connecting the two most unstable nodes. This can be achieved by finding the first PMU node with the highest SDF. If this node is not an edge node (i.e., not sharing a link with any other neighboring PDC), the PDC can then search for a neighbor node with the second highest SDF. The link/region connecting these nodes will then be rated as an "unstable link".

If the node is an edge node (e.g., node A6 in Fig. 1), the PDC, by looking at its local map, recognizes that a link assessment needs to be done at the next PDC level (e.g., RPDC in Fig.1). In order to carry out link assessment at RPDC, all local PDC will forward their row vectors to RPDC. After gathering these row vectors, the RPDC is able to generate a row vector $M^{RPDC} = (M^A \times K + M^B \times L + M^C \times Q) / (K + L + Q)$ for its covering areas A, B and C. Based on this row vector and the synchrophasor data of the abnormal PMU nodes (A6 and its neighbors A4, A5, and B1), link assessment will be carried out using the same procedure defined in equations (1)-to-(3). Bear in mind that, as described in [4], a local PDC first classifies each of its PMU nodes into two categories: normal and abnormal. Only the synchrophasor data classified as abnormal will be forward to the next PDC level [4]. Therefore, it is realistic to assume that the data for any of the A1 neighbors, if classified as abnormal, will be available at the RPDC.

Next, we assess the performance of the above scheme using the IEEE 34-bus distribution system and the IEEE 39-bus transmission system.

IV. VOLTAGE INSTABILITY DETECTION

The In a power system the state variables, such as bus voltages, bus currents, frequency, power factor and branch flows, can be measured and uploaded by PMUs. These variables can be used as measurements to assess the power disturbances such as fault occurrences. We assume a fault is the result of a short circuit at the time instant t_0 causing a bus voltage to drop. Assuming that the time of impact is short and for a PMU reporting rate of 30 measurements per second, three consecutive measurements would be sufficient to include a pre-fault ($t < t_0$), during fault ($t_0 < t < t + \tau$) and post-fault ($t > t + \tau$) events. Under these conditions the voltages measured before, at and after a fault at bus i can be sufficiently represented by the observation vector $V_i = (V_{-1,i} \ V_{0,i} \ V_{1,i})$.

To examine the performance of the fault detection based on the standard deviation, we consider the IEEE 34-bus distribution system that experiencing a voltage drop on bus-890 as shown in Fig. 2. It should be noted that a bus will be labeled as abnormal if its SDF value is bigger than a pre-defined threshold. Fig. 2

corresponds to a radial distribution and further details can be found in [9] and [10]. In our model, two wind turbines are connected to buses 848 and 890.

To construct a hierarchical structure, the system has been divided into three neighboring areas marked as areas A, B, and C (Fig. 2) where each PMU is connected to one bus. Link between Bus 816 and 824 corresponds to the shared link between areas A and B, while the link between Bus 858 and 834 is a connecting link between areas B and C. The voltages at three consecutive time instances would represent a 3-D observation vector. Table 2 shows the proposed mapping scheme for the IEEE 34-bus distribution system, which includes calculated SDFs according to (3) and GIFs according to (4) for all areas.

Most power distribution networks have a tree-like topology with power injection referred to as the feeder. The IEEE 34-bus distribution system shown in Fig. 2 is a typical example with tree topology. Its configuration and details are defined in [9] and [10]. In our simulation, two wind turbines are connected to buses 848 and 890. PMUs are deployed on every bus to measure state variables and the synchrophasor measurements are then sent to local PDCs and central PDC through the hierarchical synchrophasor network.

As indicated in Fig. 2, a fault occurs on bus-890. The positive sequence voltage vectors $V_i = (V_{-1,i} \ V_{0,i} \ V_{1,i})$ of monitored buses, as well as the corresponding SDF values are displayed in Table 2. In this system, the threshold is set to 0.2. This is based on a large number of experiments that place faults at different locations. The dendrogram of classification analysis [11] based on the buses' SDF values has also been used to highlight the classification performance. The standard deviation field based instability detection is carried out in areas A, B and C separately. In area B, bus-890 has the highest deviation value of 0.5302, which is significantly larger than the threshold with a GIF of 0.1624. As can be observed, other buses act in a similar manner, but with much smaller deviation values. The corresponding dendrogram of cluster analysis based on area B's SDFs is shown in Fig. 3. Obviously, the status of bus-890 is distinct and can be firmly classified as an abnormal bus. It is reasonable to conclude that bus-890 is experiencing difficulties. In areas A and C all buses act consistently and their corresponding GIFs are 0.0387 and 0.0134, which is much smaller than that of area B. Hence they are free from any disturbance. Since bus-890 is an internal node in area B and has no connection with PMUs belonging to other areas, a next level assessment by RPDC won't be necessary. This result demonstrates that events occurring on the distribution system will significantly impact the voltage magnitude and are limited in a small area, only visible to nearby PMUs [12].

In our next set of experiments we consider the IEEE 39-Bus model shown in Fig. 4 [13, 14]. In the first set of experiments, the IEEE 39-Bus system is treated as one area and the disturbance detection is carried out in RPDC. The negative sequence voltage vectors for all buses and their corresponding SDFs (as well as its GIF) are displayed in Table 3. As shown in this table, bus-18 has the highest SDF value of 0.155. This is significantly larger than the group GIF of 0.0369. Bus-18's neighbors, i.e., 17 and 3, have the second and third highest SDF values of 0.0861 and 0.0604. Then a further away neighbor: bus

Fig. 2: Deviation field of an IEEE 34-bus distribution system experiencing a voltage drop on bus-890.

Table 2: Disturbance detection for the IEEE 34-bus distribution system

	Bus	V_{-1}	V_0	V_{-1}	SDF	GIF
Area A	1 800	1	0.9210	0.9210	0.0625	0.0387
	2 802	1	0.9044	0.9044	0.0390	
	3 806	1	0.8631	0.8631	0.0194	
	4 808	1	0.8749	0.8749	0.0027	
	5 810	1	0.9016	0.9016	0.0350	
	6 812	1	0.8976	0.8976	0.0294	
	7 814	1	0.8913	0.8913	0.0205	
	8 850	1	0.8832	0.8832	0.0090	
	9 816	1	0.8625	0.8625	0.0203	
	10 818	1	0.8348	0.8348	0.0594	
	11 820	1	0.8601	0.8601	0.0273	
	12 822	1	0.8274	0.8274	0.0699	
Area B	13 824	1	0.8718	0.8718	0.0336	0.1624
	14 826	1	0.8910	0.8910	0.0608	
	15 828	1	0.8351	0.8351	0.0183	
	16 830	1	0.8637	0.8637	0.0222	
	17 854	1	0.9016	0.9016	0.0758	
	18 856	1	0.8827	0.8827	0.0490	
	19 852	1	0.8762	0.8762	0.0398	
	20 832	1	0.8934	0.8934	0.0642	
	21 888	1	0.9221	0.9221	0.1048	
	22 890	1	0.4731	0.4731	0.5302	
	23 858	1	0.8764	0.8764	0.0401	
	24 864	1	0.8892	0.8892	0.0582	
Area C	25 834	1	0.9125	0.9125	0.0022	0.0134
	26 842	1	0.9037	0.9037	0.0102	
	27 844	1	0.9264	0.9264	0.0219	
	28 846	1	0.9058	0.9058	0.0072	
	29 848	1	0.8963	0.8963	0.0207	
	30 860	1	0.9017	0.9017	0.0130	
	31 836	1	0.9148	0.9148	0.0055	
	32 840	1	0.9271	0.9271	0.0229	
	33 862	1	0.9086	0.9086	0.0033	
	34 838	1	0.9122	0.9122	0.0018	

27, has a SDF value of 0.0529. The link between buses 18 and 17 can be marked as "unstable link or region". The remaining buses have relatively low deviations. As expected, the faulty bus behaves abnormally with high deviation value, which also affect its neighboring buses. Note that events that occurs on the transmission system can be observed by multiple PMUs in a large area [12]. This further proves the accuracy of the observed standard deviation field shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3: The dendrogram of bus deviation values in area B, IEEE 34-bus distribution system.

To assess the hierarchical disturbance detection, in our next experiment the IEEE 39-bus transmission system is divided into local regions: A, B, C, and D (see Fig. 4). Since the area A has a GIF value of 0.0661s, which is much larger than the predefined threshold value of 0.03, it is then classified as “unstable local area”. In this area, bus-18 has highest SDF value 0.1396. By checking local map, PDC-A will recognize that Bus-18 is an edge node connecting to Bus-17 of area C. After labeling Bus-18 and its neighbors Bus-3 as abnormal, PDC-A will forward their synchrophasor data and the row vector to the next PDC level for further link assessment. Similarly, the area C having a GIF value 0.0333 can detect that Bus-17 has the highest SDF value of 0.0674 and is connected to Bus-18 of area A (an edge Bus). PDC-C will then forward Bus-17 and its neighbor bus-27’s synchrophasor data as well as its row vector to RPDC for further link assessment. The RPDC will then reassess the synchrophasor data for Buses 18, 3, 17, and 27 according to equations (1)-to-(3). Note that the Areas B and D are free from disturbance as all their Buses work consistently with low SDFs. Their row vectors will be sent to RPDC for a further regional link assessment. Based on the row vectors from all areas, RPDC is able to derive a new row vector $M^{RPDC} = [0 \ 0.0364 \ 0.0364]$ and evaluate link status, as shown in Table 5. As displayed in Table 5, Bus-18 has the highest SDF value of 0.155, followed by Bus-17 with an SDF value of 0.0861 and Bus-3 with an SDF value 0.0604. Again, the link between buses 18 and 17 can be marked as “unstable link or region”. These results indicate that hierarchical disturbance detection in our second set of experiments achieves the same performance as in the first set of experiments. This result illustrates that the proposed hierarchical algorithm is capable of locating the instable region in a distributed manner with greatly reduced computation without involving areas that are functioning properly.

V. CONCLUSION

Power quality disturbances and ways to control them has been one of the more challenging issues in smart grid. While distinguishing between voltage interruptions caused by a fault or other disturbance has been in the forefront of research activities, in this paper we have developed a strategy that is capable of identifying regions that suffer from a rapid voltage drop. This strategy, which is based on a combination of hierarchical network structure and a voltage tracking and classification algorithm, has been shown to be very effective in detecting a source of grid instability.

Fig. 4 IEEE 39-bus transmission system experiencing voltage drop on bus-18.

Table 3: Disturbance detection for IEEE 39-bus system

Bus	V_{-1}	V_0	V_{-1}	SDF	GIF
Bus-1	0	0.0202	0.0202	0.0229	0.0369
Bus-2	0	0.0471	0.0471	0.0151	
Bus-3	0	0.0791	0.0791	0.0604	
Bus-4	0	0.0387	0.0387	0.0032	
Bus-5	0	0.026	0.026	0.0147	
Bus-6	0	0.0247	0.0247	0.0166	
Bus-7	0	0.0213	0.0213	0.0214	
Bus-8	0	0.0206	0.0206	0.0224	
Bus-9	0	0.0106	0.0106	0.0365	
Bus-10	0	0.0268	0.0268	0.0136	
Bus-11	0	0.0261	0.0261	0.0146	
Bus-12	0	0.0257	0.0257	0.0152	
Bus-13	0	0.0294	0.0294	0.0099	
Bus-14	0	0.0364	0.0364	0	
Bus-15	0	0.0472	0.0472	0.0152	
Bus-16	0	0.0568	0.0568	0.0288	
Bus-17	0	0.0973	0.0973	0.0861	
Bus-18	0	0.146	0.146	0.1550	
Bus-19	0	0.0302	0.0302	0.0088	
Bus-20	0	0.0177	0.0177	0.0265	
Bus-21	0	0.042	0.042	0.0079	
Bus-22	0	0.0326	0.0326	0.0054	
Bus-23	0	0.0324	0.0324	0.0057	
Bus-24	0	0.0542	0.0542	0.0251	
Bus-25	0	0.043	0.043	0.0093	
Bus-26	0	0.0572	0.0572	0.0294	
Bus-27	0	0.0738	0.0738	0.0529	
Bus-28	0	0.0404	0.0404	0.0056	
Bus-29	0	0.0355	0.0355	0.0013	
Bus-30	0	0.0242	0.0242	0.0173	
Bus-31	0	0.0148	0.0148	0.0306	
Bus-32	0	0.0159	0.0159	0.0290	
Bus-33	0	0.0188	0.0188	0.0249	
Bus-34	0	0.0145	0.0145	0.0310	
Bus-35	0	0.0221	0.0221	0.0203	
Bus-36	0	0.0175	0.0175	0.0268	
Bus-37	0	0.0258	0.0258	0.0150	
Bus-38	0	0.0244	0.0244	0.0170	
Bus-39	0	0.0036	0.0036	0.0464	

Table 4: Hierarchical disturbance detection for IEEE 39-bus system

	Bus	V_{-1}	V_0	V_{-1}	SDF	GIF
Area A	Bus-1	0	0.0202	0.0202	0.0383	0.0661
	Bus-2	0	0.0471	0.0471	0.0002	
	Bus-3	0	0.0791	0.0791	0.0450	
	Bus-9	0	0.0106	0.0106	0.0518	
	Bus-18	0	0.146	0.146	0.1396	
	Bus-30	0	0.0242	0.0242	0.0326	
	Bus-39	0	0.0036	0.0036	0.0617	
Area B	Bus-4	0	0.0387	0.0387	0.0186	0.0097
	Bus-5	0	0.026	0.026	0.0007	
	Bus-6	0	0.0247	0.0247	0.0012	
	Bus-7	0	0.0213	0.0213	0.0060	
	Bus-8	0	0.0206	0.0206	0.0070	
	Bus-10	0	0.0268	0.0268	0.0018	
	Bus-11	0	0.0261	0.0261	0.0008	
	Bus-12	0	0.0257	0.0257	0.0002	
	Bus-13	0	0.0294	0.0294	0.0055	
	Bus-14	0	0.0364	0.0364	0.0154	
	Bus-31	0	0.0148	0.0148	0.0152	
	Bus-32	0	0.0159	0.0159	0.0136	
	Area C	Bus-17	0	0.0973	0.0973	
Bus-25		0	0.043	0.043	0.0094	
Bus-26		0	0.0572	0.0572	0.0106	
Bus-27		0	0.0738	0.0738	0.0341	
Bus-28		0	0.0404	0.0404	0.0131	
Bus-29		0	0.0355	0.0355	0.0200	
Area D	Bus-37	0	0.0258	0.0258	0.0338	0.0201
	Bus-38	0	0.0244	0.0244	0.0357	
	Bus-15	0	0.0472	0.0472	0.0213	
	Bus-16	0	0.0568	0.0568	0.0348	
	Bus-19	0	0.0302	0.0302	0.0028	
	Bus-20	0	0.0177	0.0177	0.0205	
	Bus-21	0	0.042	0.042	0.0139	
	Bus-22	0	0.0326	0.0326	0.0006	
	Bus-23	0	0.0324	0.0324	0.0003	
	Bus-24	0	0.0542	0.0542	0.0312	
Bus-33	0	0.0188	0.0188	0.0189		
Bus-34	0	0.0145	0.0145	0.0250		
Bus-35	0	0.0221	0.0221	0.0142		
Bus-36	0	0.0175	0.0175	0.0207		

Table 5: Link assessment in RPDC for IEEE 39-bus system

Bus	V_{-1}	V_0	V_{-1}	SDF
M^{RPDC}	0	0.0364	0.0364	0
Bus-3	0	0.0791	0.0791	0.0604
Bus-17	0	0.0973	0.0973	0.0861
Bus-18	0	0.146	0.146	0.1550
Bus-27	0	0.0738	0.0738	0.0529

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